

SCIENTIFIC-THEORETICAL BASIS OF DEVELOPMENT OF
INFORMATION TECHNOLOGICAL COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS OF
HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS OF PEDAGOGY

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Аннотация: В данной статье описаны научно-теоретические основы развития информационно-технологических компетенций и профессиональной подготовки студентов педагогических высших учебных заведений. В статье раскрыты методические основы обеспечения будущих педагогов педагогическими условиями, формирования их профессиональных компетенций и организации профессиональной деятельности.

Ключевые слова: педагогика, высшее образование, информатика, компетентность, профессиональная компетентность, информационная компетентность.

Abstract: This article describes the scientific-theoretical foundations of the development of information technology competences and professional training of students in higher educational institutions of pedagogy. The article explains the methodological foundations of providing future pedagogues with pedagogical conditions, forming their professional competences and organizing their professional activities.

Key words: pedagogy, higher education, informatics, competence, professional competence, information competence,

From a psychological point of view, the main feature of activity is its objectivity. The object of activity, according to these theories, is not only an object of nature, but also an object of culture, in which a certain socially developed method of action is determined. This method is repeated each time a person performs an objective activity. As S.D. Smirnov noted, "this feature reflects the conditioning of the activity process by the external world (material and ideal) and the direction of the development of the activity itself and its subject is aimed at the development of new subjects, the introduction of increasingly stronger subjects will do."

Human activity has a productive nature, that is, it is always aimed at changing the natural or social reality. In the most general sense, professional

activity is understood as a type of skilled human activity, and it also includes the process of changing its subject.

Professional activity is characterized by the characteristics that psychologists use to describe any other activity and that we indicated above. The relationship between the concepts of "activity" and "professional activity" is implemented through the concept of "work". In a broad psychological sense, work is one of the main types of human activity.

We can say that the theoretical problems of professional activity are well developed, but in practice, approaches to evaluating its results and efficiency are required. The professional activity of a modern specialist in any field is characterized by the need to process a large amount of various information, to act in uncertain situations, to make decisions in the absence of complete information or in a short time, under stress. In addition, work and occupation are also economic categories.

In the history of the development of labor psychology, career guidance and organizational psychology, in solving this problem, professional selection, selection of professional personnel, suitability for the profession, professional adaptation, professionally important qualities and skills with sufficient experience in other areas, professional and psychographic approaches, expert models, qualification requirements - these and other problems are fully developed in domestic and foreign subjects and are used in the practice of teaching higher education students.

However, in our opinion, they cannot serve as a practical tool for performance evaluation, as they often require in-depth psychological training. Of course, a number of companies may have sufficiently qualified personnel evaluation specialists in their employees, but even in this case, the evaluation criteria are not always completely clear to the employer and the employee. Therefore, the idea of developing professional performance evaluation indicators, which include the above experience and are more clearly observable and measurable, is not accidental. To date, competencies work as such indicators. They are not ideal metrics, but they serve the needs of performance evaluation based on observability and compliance with measurement criteria.

J. Newton "identifies three main components of behavior:

- the situation in which the individual finds himself;
- the goal that the person wants to achieve;
- actions necessary to achieve the goal.

These three components of behavior correspond to three stages of the general behavior process:

1. Building a behavioral world, that is, processing information about the physical environment in describing a meaningful situation faced by the subject himself.

2. Transforming the subject's dynamic relationship with the world (that is, his needs) into structures of objects, goals, and "means-ends" or plans of behavior.

3. The performance or performance of actions necessary to achieve the specified internal or external goals.

In the process of preparing students for professional activities, various tasks are solved, but one of them, in our opinion, is not being solved sufficiently - this is the task of preparing a specialist to work in a specific workplace. From the point of view of labor psychology, it is customary to distinguish between the concepts of "occupation" and "workplace". There are traditional and innovative interpretations of the profession. The first group includes: the field of application of human forces as a labor subject, the type of labor activity as a result of the existing division of labor; a group of people performing socially important functions corresponding to the type of work; the level of training that allows the person to perform the relevant labor functions; activity performed by a person for a certain reward; activity that ensures that a person has a certain status in society.

The second group represents competencies related to social interactions of people. This group includes competencies: social interaction (tolerance, cooperation, partnership, social mobility), communication skills (oral and written speech, dialogue

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